

Distributed Aperture Implementation on the TechSat 21 Satellites

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Abstract—The Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL) initiated the TechSat 21 flight experiment to demonstrate the concept of performing space missions for less overall cost using formations of small satellites that operate cooperatively to perform the function of a larger, single satellite. TechSat 21 is short for Technology Satellite of the 21st Century; the program began as a joint initiative of the Office of Scientific Research, Space Vehicles, Sensors, and Propulsion Directorates. Each satellite within the formation is designed to communicate with the others and share relative navigation, processing, payload operations, data downlink, and other mission functions.

The flight experiment was conceived as 3 satellites flying in formation to create a large, reconfigurable sparse aperture antenna system. The experiment was designed to address stressing challenges of distributed aperture radar and to provide a technology base for a variety of missions that include RF imaging, moving target indication, geolocation, anti-jamming, and terrain elevation. Key experiment objectives include demonstration of formation maintenance and reconfiguration, autonomous formation control, and multi-mission sparse aperture sensing.

The Preliminary Design Review (PDR) was held in April 2001, and the Bus Critical Design Review (CDR) was held in Oct 2002. A concept analysis segment of the program addresses challenges related to the processing of sparse distributed aperture data, precision formation control, and cost performance analyses.

An overview of the TechSat 21 concept, flight experiment objectives, and satellite description is presented along with a discussion of the challenges and solutions for implementing a distributed aperture RF antenna array in such areas as relative metrology, formation maintenance, and signal processing for varied mission applications. This paper also discusses the subsystem requirements derived from the desired performance goals and the hardware and software implementation necessary to achieve these requirements.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The availability of very capable satellites with high performance per cost and weight, in particular the emerging nano- and micro-satellites, could enable new, and cheaper, ways of doing business in space. One such concept uses a cluster of satellites that fly in formation and cooperate to perform a mission. The required functionality is spread across the satellites in the cluster, the aggregate forming a "virtual satellite." [1] The satellites maintain constant communication and monitor each other, so that they can maneuver and stay in formation by virtue of simple low effort cluster orbits. [2] Part of this vision is that the mission and sensor processing, health and status, command and control functions are distributed amongst the members of the cluster.

A potential application of these clusters is to synthesize a large aperture. Since the satellites are not connected by structures, they can be separated over very large baselines that could not be considered for monolithic apertures. This feature may benefit such missions as space based radar, which typically requires large power-aperture products to achieve acceptable area coverage rates or large apertures for detection of slow moving targets in clutter. Another possible mission application is mobile or jam resistant communications, which benefit from narrow beam widths and tailorable beam patterns associated with large apertures. Other applications, such as interferometric imaging or source detection and geolocation may benefit from the large and tailorable baselines afforded by these distributed satellite systems. [3]

This system architecture is also appealing for its adaptability. Since neither the geometry of the cluster or the number of satellites in the cluster needs to remain fixed, the cluster configuration can be changed to suit a particular mission need. The adaptability of such an approach is attractive for high value, high cost missions. The system performance can be slowly increased over time with a phased deployment and tailored to meet evolving threats or world conditions. Furthermore, the deployment cost can be spread over a number of years, while still providing acceptable but ever increasing levels of performance. Optimization of the cluster geometry by modifying the baselines or shifting satellites between clusters has the potential to permit other missions to be performed, or to adapt to a particular mission application (e.g., a new target characteristic or revisit time requirement).

Given these potential benefits offered by a distributed satellite system, there are numerous technical challenges to be addressed to make an operational system viable using this architecture. First, very precise metrology must be implemented to cohere multiple phase centers over a large virtual aperture. Second, new algorithms must be developed that exploit the advantages of large spatial separation to overcome processing losses associated with sparsely filled apertures. Third, there are unique problems related to distributing and processing sensor information from multiple satellites. Also, operational systems have very demanding requirements so that trying to put multiple missions on a single satellite may not be viable – perhaps the only practical role will be as a short-term gap-filler or in special tactical situations. Last, these capabilities need to compete favorably from an overall system cost point of view, to realize an overall benefit from the added complexity the approach entails. The complexity of the system trade space driven by these issues, as well as the need to determine the cost benefit of such a revolutionary approach, are critical drivers in the overall program schedule.

2. ORIGINAL CONCEPT

The original TechSat 21 concept was born out of a number of studies and was first documented by Das et. al. in 1998 and is elucidated below. [3, 4] A conceptual system design for a virtual satellite approach to the reference radar mission was developed by the Aerospace Corporation’s CDC to meet the requirements of the reference mission (Table 1). A technology freeze date of 2005 was selected with a system IOC of 2010 and a mission life of 10 years.

Table 1. Reference Mission Requirements

	GMTI	SAR (10m)
Access	Global	<85deg Lat.
Coverage	2 Theaters (1000km ² ea.)	
Theater Update Rate	20min	20min
Target RCS	10dBsm	-
MDV	1.7m/s	-
Area Coverage Rate	2000km ² /s	1000km ² /s

For the conceptual system, thirty-five clusters of eight satellites each (plus 40 spares) were employed in a highly inclined Walker constellation of 7 orbital planes at 800 km to provide global coverage with minimal outages. The data dissemination function would rely on geo-synchronous relay satellites assumed to exist in the mission timeframe. The overall system architecture is fairly conventional, with each cluster “acting” as a single satellite. However, the individual satellite design and the virtual satellite system were both of a very innovative design, as illustrated below in Figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1 – TechSat 21 Satellite Conceptual Design

Figure 2 – TechSat 21 Conceptual Cluster

A dedicated mission control center was assumed for this system, and points-of-presence at the Air Force Satellite Control Network, Relay Control and Tasking Facility, and the Joint Command Payload Center. A dedicated operations training center and two mobile ground stations with mission processing capability are also part of the system. A staff of 360 government and 90 contractor personnel performs operations and maintenance of the system.

The original satellite design could be launched in groups of eight from a Taurus or Athena launch vehicle. Multiple clusters can be launched together with larger launchers, although the system design did not account for (in terms of cost reduction or increased deployment pace) these potential operational scenarios.

The weight of the conceptual design, using technologies that would be available in 2005-2010, was estimated to be close to 100kg. Total life cycle costs were estimated and appeared to offer potential savings over traditional single satellite approaches due to mass production of the microsattellites and lower launch costs. The TechSat 21 flight experiment was initiated to assess this potential for mass and cost savings, characterize performance of distributed apertures, and to demonstrate enabling technologies for distributed satellite operation.

3. EXPERIMENT OBJECTIVES

The TechSat 21 flight experiment was designed as a formation of three low-mass (~150kg) satellites to demonstrate enabling technologies for microsattellites and distributed satellite sensor systems and to assess potential utility for affordable and robust multi-mission operations. Experiment objectives include demonstrating low cost, lightweight subsystems, precision formation flying, autonomous operation, formation reconfiguration, precision metrology, and sparse aperture sensing algorithms. [5]

The TechSat 21 flight experiment concept is depicted in Figure 3 and was designed to evaluate hardware, software, metrology, and mission data associated with implementation of a distributed aperture system. Cost and performance constraints for the flight experiment would have limited such operational metrics as total sensor collection time, onboard processing, detectable target size, area coverage rate, and data dissemination, but the projected performance was initially deemed sufficient to extrapolate to full operational requirements and to show the required subsystem capabilities.

Figure 3 – TechSat 21 Flight Experiment

If the initial flight experiment demonstrated sufficient performance and user utility, a follow-on flight demonstration could focus on meeting user requirements with a satellite designed to meet realistic operational duty cycles with on-board processing and operational target algorithms and user interfaces, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4 – Capability Demonstration

Finally, an operational distributed system, conceptually depicted in Figure 5 below, must meet such operational performance metrics as area coverage rates, revisit rates, probability of detection, image resolution, operational

frequencies, multi-platform compatibility, etc. Each potential mission application, such as ground moving target indication, geolocation, RF imaging, anti-jamming, secure communications, and digital terrain elevation, will have unique requirements that will need to be incorporated into the satellite design.

Figure 5 – Conceptual Operational System

4. SATELLITE DESCRIPTION

Based upon the experiment objectives and associated design requirements, the original conceptual satellite design consisted of a hexagonal bus with six solar arrays and flew in a gravity gradient orientation with the RF payload-facing nadir. This design was shown in Figures 1 & 2 and was the design presented at the System Requirements Review in September 2000.

Subsequent detailed analysis of the design showed that the design was not stable in the gravity gradient orientation, the solar array was not mass efficient, and the configuration did not meet launch vehicle size and mass constraints. As a result, new space vehicle configurations were developed and analyzed.

The current baseline design was presented at the Critical Design Review (CDR) in October 2002 and is referred to as solar inertial (SI) since the vehicle trajectory is perpendicular to the orbit plane and rotates about the solar array axis to track the sun and the satellite points nadir while in eclipse (to reduce thermal losses of the payload antenna). The SI design has a center bus with two opposing solar arrays shown in Figure 6.

With the thin-film solar arrays unfolded, the satellite dimensions become approximately 6.3m x 2.3m x 0.8m. In the stowed configuration for launch, the dimensions of each satellite are 1.0m x 0.8m x 0.7m, as illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 6 – TechSat 21 Flight Experiment Satellite

A key objective of the satellite design was to keep the mass as close to 100kg as possible. To do this, the spacecraft leverages numerous development programs for advanced, lightweight subsystems at AFRL, DARPA, JPL, and NASA Goddard. This has enabled a very capable satellite with a current best estimate for satellite mass of 152kg with 70kg for the payload and 82kg for the bus. The prime contractor for the satellite design, fabrication, and test is MicroSat Systems Inc. in Denver CO. The highlights of each of the SI subsystems are described in the following sections.

Figure 7 – TechSat 21 Stowed Configuration

Attitude Determination, and Control

The Attitude Determination, and Control Subsystem (ADCS) is being developed by Advanced Solutions Inc. and implements attitude determination using one 3-axis magnetometer, three analog sun sensors (Figure 8), and one star tracker. Nominal operation requires no more than 2.5 degrees attitude knowledge, and payload data collects achieve the required 0.05-degree attitude knowledge using

the star tracker. The star tracker, shown in Figure 8, has lost-in-space capability, tracks 5 stars, and has an accuracy of 0.0028deg cross boresight and 0.02deg about boresight.

Figure 8 – ADCS Attitude Determination Components (BATC CT-633 Star Tracker, Goodrich 13-515 Sun Sensors, and Billingsley ZFM100S Magnetometer).

Three-axis attitude control requirement of 0.5-1.0 degree is achieved with three 1.0N-m-s reaction wheels and three magnetic torque rods, shown in Figure 9, achieving attitude control to less than a degree.

Figure 9 – Microcosm MT-15-1 Torque Rods (linear dipole moment of 15 Am² and a saturation moment >20 Am²).

Primary modes of operation are: maintain sun pointing of solar arrays for power collection, point payload antenna at nadir during eclipse for thermal management, point payload antenna for data collects, point spacecraft for delta-V maneuvers, and support initialization and safe mode operations. [5]

Command and Data Handling (C&DH)

The C&DH subsystem is being developed by BroadReach Engineering and consists of a 133MHz Rad 750 processor with 128MByte RAM and 256KByte EEPROM. It uses compact peripheral component interconnect (cPCI) for synchronous 32-bit data transfer at 33MHz. There are four 3U boards: flight processor, communications and payload interface, state of health monitor and attitude control interface, and power conversion. Some of the major technology features of the C&DH subsystem include:

XILINX reconfigurable FPGA (mass storage module), 3U cPCI system based on 133MHz PowerPC 750 CPU, 330 front panel I/O using micro-D and nano connectors, next generation composite chassis (MicroSat Systems Inc.), autonomous HW SOH reporting and commanding without CPU, 160GBytes of non-volatile storage (640Mbps record, 160Mbps playback, <4kg), and the full C&DH packaged in less than 213 cubic inches (includes 2 spare slots). The C&DH box is composite on an aluminum baseplate for a total weight of 2.5kg for the C&DH unit, shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 – Integrated C&DH Box Engineering Model.

Its average operating power is 30 watts. The C&DH has a RS-422 interface to an external 160GByte mass memory unit comprised of mass memory controller board, mass memory power board, and eight 20GByte hard drives (required to support 160Mbps data rates during payload operation). The mass memory unit weighs 3.1kg and requires 80 watts power. The Engineering Model of the Mass Storage Module is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 – Mass Storage Module Engineering Unit (Non-Volatile Data Storage, 160 Gbytes using 8 Commercial 2.5in ATA Hard Drives, 422 Command/Data I/F at 460.8kbps, LVDS Data Interface at 640Mbps/160Mbps).

The C&DH provides computing support for command and telemetry data, attitude determination and control, navigation, formation control, thermal control, payload commanding, data transfer, mass memory management, and spacecraft timing calculations.

Electrical Power

The electrical power subsystem (EPS) employs direct energy transfer architecture, 1.5kW peak power capability, power management capability (32 switched loads), autonomous battery charge control, and autonomous load shed and is being developed by BroadReach Engineering.

The electrical power subsystem consists of thin-film solar arrays using copper indium gallium diselenide (CIGS) on stainless steel substrate, shown in Figure 12.

The two solar arrays have a total area of 10m² and provide 960 watt power output at 8.5% efficiency at beginning of life with a projected 5.8% efficiency at end of life. The total mass of the arrays is 8.5kg and includes an innovative and very lightweight deployment concept called Fold Integrated Thin-film Stiffener (FITS).

An 8-cell lithium polymer battery provides 1600 watt-hours (48 amp-hours) to support 430 watts on-orbit average power at no more than 25% depth of discharge. It also supports maximum power output of 1500 watts for durations of up to 10 minutes to support radar data collects. The battery weighs 14kg and the power control electronics are an additional 4kg.

Figure 12 – Full Scale Solar Array Deployment Testing.

Communications

Alternative approaches were considered for the intersatellite communications and telemetry, tracking and command (TT&C) subsystem. The current subsystem is based IIT-AES's Low Power Transceiver (LPT) that has S- and L-band receive, S-band transmit, as well as GPS receive capability. In this customized LPT system the S-band supports both intersatellite communications and TT&C.

Relatively low data rates of 160Kbps are used for intersatellite communications to pass position and timing information to support formation flying and sparse aperture payload operations.

The TT&C data rates are 100Kbps uplink and 1Mbps downlink. The experiment data is downlinked using X-band payload antenna for a high bandwidth downlink at 160Mbps. The TT&C, GPS, and intersatellite communications system are all integrated into the LPT module stack, shown in Figure 13. The mass of the communications expected to be approximately 4kg and includes the LPT unit, antennas, mounting hardware, couplers, connectors and wiring harness.

The LPT uses a spread spectrum waveform for intersatellite communication that provides for both data transfer and centimeter-level satellite-to-satellite range estimation. [6] The absolute and relative navigation enhanced subsystem is called the Telecommunications, Crosslink, and GPS Subsystem (TCGS) and the relative navigation components are discussed in greater detail in the section on distributed aperture implementation.

Figure 13 – Exploded View of LPT Module Stack.

Propulsion

Each satellite has a single Hall effect thruster (HET) developed by TRW that provides variable thrust, 1370 sec specific impulse, and 35% efficiency, shown in Figure 14. The dry mass of the thruster, electronics, and fuel system is 7.8kg, and 1 kg of xenon fuel provides sufficient margin on the nominal 65 m/sec mission requirement for each spacecraft. This is sufficient for 1 year operation that includes formation initialization, maintenance, and several reconfigurations between 5km formations to smaller 100m formations and from linear to non-planar elliptical formations.

Figure 14 – HET Engineering Model and Firing ($I_{sp} = 1370s$, Thrust = 12.2mN, Mass = 7.8kg, Power = 377W).

RF Payload

The payload is an X-band $2.0m^2$ 2-D electronically steered antenna (ESA) with effective radiated power of over 150 watts. The current best estimate of the mass including antennas, receiver electronics unit (REU), support structure, and deployment hinges is 70kg. The payload has a single channel receiver with a programmable waveform generator. Most of the REU boards are modified for space operations and environment from existing F-16 antenna receiver/exciter control electronics. The payload also provides high bandwidth communications downlink at 160Mbps to commercial X-band satellite ground stations. Two minutes of payload operation at 640Mbps generates 10GBytes of sensor data. Under normal operations this data will be downlinked over a period of 3-4 days but could be downlinked in a single day at existing ground sites if necessary. Average payload power consumption during radar collects is 930 watts for 2 minutes and for payload data downlink is 600 watts for contact periods of up to 10 minutes.

5. IMPLEMENTATION

To enable distributed aperture operation, depicted in Figure 15, the first step is to design an intersatellite metrology system that supports mission data collection and processing. In general, to coherently process across a distributed aperture, the phase information must be aligned to within $1/10^{th}$ to $1/20^{th}$ of a wavelength. This enables the satellites to operate as a “virtual aperture” and for individual satellite images to be combined to form a higher resolution single image.

Figure 15 – TechSat 21 Sparse Aperture Operation Concept.

Metrology Approach

The intersatellite metrology system consists of a multi-tier approach with increasing timing performance as shown in Table 2. It uses the communications subsystem and navigation software for tiers 0-1, the metrology subsystem consisting of an ultrastable oscillator and X-band antennas for tier 2, and ground processing techniques for tier 3.

The GPS provides absolute timing to $\pm 100nsec$, differential GPS provides relative position knowledge of $\pm 10cm$ and timing to $\pm 20nsec$, and an ultra stable oscillator provides local time precision of $\pm 5psec$ over the maximum signal integration time of 5sec. Intersatellite communications regularly update position and timing measurements, and on-board extended Kalman filters maintain best estimates of absolute and relative time and position. Prior to data collect, a series of payload synchronization pulses improve relative position knowledge and timing an order of magnitude to $\pm 1cm$ and $\pm 50psec$, respectively. The on-orbit requirement for relative timing is $\pm 200nsec$ to synchronize payload transmissions from the three satellite payloads for sparse aperture sensing. The higher precision measurements are used in time interval correlation extended Kalman filter post-processing to align phase information to within one wavelength so that signal processing techniques can coherently align the sensor data from the three satellite payloads within $1/20$ of a wavelength to create a single image from the three satellite “virtual aperture.” [5]

Table 2. Metrology Tiers.

Tier	Accuracy	Method
0	+/- 100ns	GPS and Absolute Navigation Software (AbsNav SW)
1	+/- 20ns	Differential GPS and Relative Navigation Software (RelNav SW)
2	+/- 50ps	Pre-collection Synchronization Pulses
3	+/- 5 ps	Indirect Clutter and Image Co-registration

Differential GPS and Relative Navigation

ITT's Low Power Transceiver (LPT) provides differential GPS for relative position and velocity information and intersatellite communication that provides a one-way cross range measurement as well as transmits position and timing information. The LPT provides tens of centimeters accuracy in position, sub-millimeter accuracy in velocity, and tens of nanoseconds accuracy in clock knowledge (each one sigma). GEODE is used for estimating the absolute state and for steering the LPT clock. Due to the flight-critical nature of the navigation function, the navigation software is hosted on the spacecraft's radiation hardened processor rather than internal to the LPT. [6] Each of the three spacecraft host identical navigation software and compute relative states to the other two spacecraft rather than having a central processing spacecraft.

The relative navigation filter processes double-differenced GPS L1 carrier measurements and one-way cross-range carrier measurements to estimate the relative position and velocity. The carrier ambiguity is not resolved in the raw carrier measurements but is carried through to the double-differenced carrier measurements (so that any hardware biases are canceled) where it is estimated using a decision-based integer ambiguity resolution technique. [7]

The relative navigation filter's equations of motion and propagation equations are formulated in terms of the relative ECI state rather than as the difference between the absolute states. Differential accelerations are modeled for the Earth's point mass, maneuvers, and the Earth's oblateness.

The relative navigation clock filter processes single-difference carrier measurements between the spacecraft. Similar to the relative positioning filter, the composite carrier ambiguity in the single difference measurement is estimated using the decision-based integer ambiguity resolution technique. Given a relative position accuracy error of 10 cm, carrier noise of 1 cm (actual expected to be less than 3 mm), and assuming the correct integer ambiguity has been resolved, knowledge of the relative clock accuracies on the order of a nanosecond can be achieved. However, since the crosslink data is typically processed 2

measurement cycles later (2 seconds), the relative clock offset must be propagated to current time for use by the spacecraft systems.

Distributed Aperture Sensing Modes

While the satellite formations slowly evolve over time, a broad variety of waveforms and sensor modes can be tested against numerous mission applications. When the full suite of sensing experiments have been completed, sensing performance will be characterized for the complete range of formation geometries, sizes, clutter environments, and mission applications. Experiment performance for different mission applications is expected to vary based on satellite separation. For example, large satellite separations are better for geolocation, bistatic synthetic aperture radar (SAR), and interferometric SAR (IF-SAR), and close proximity formations better for vernier on transmit SAR and GMTI.

Basic sparse aperture sensor operation consists of the three satellite payloads forming three independent receive and transmit phase centers. Each satellite payload transmits distinguishable signals (frequency, coding, or other), and each satellite receives its own return plus the returns from the other two satellite payloads. Each payload is capable of independent SAR image formation in addition to sparse aperture operation. This provides a performance reference for both conventional and distributed operation. This stand-alone operation will also be useful in the event of payload anomalies to help isolate which spacecraft has degraded performance. Sparse aperture modes of operation and the position and timing requirements discussed previously generally apply to SAR and GMTI. Such applications as geolocation have entirely different transmit modes and timing sensitivities. Each sensing mode, whether for the same or different mission applications, will have entirely different waveforms and signal processing algorithms. Given the broad range of sensing experiments, a subset of baseline waveforms and signal processing algorithms will be developed by AFRL, and the balance of experiments will be designed and post-processed by various customer organizations.

Planned sensing modes (Figure 16) include vernier on transmit SAR, single-pass interferometric SAR (IF-SAR), along-track displaced phase center antenna (DPCA) GMTI, sparse aperture GMTI, bistatic space-time adaptive processing (STAP) GMTI, electronic protection from interference sources, time delay of arrival (TDOA) geolocation, frequency delay of arrival (FDOA) geolocation, secure communication, tactical downlink to theatre, and cross cueing between signal detection/geolocation and fixed target imaging.

The experiment was designed to assess technical feasibility and was expected to show some capability in each of the modes. However, constraints imposed by this distributed

architecture such as stringent metrology requirements, reduced area coverage rates, and increased processing time may prove to be unfeasible for realistic operational requirements. Recent analyses of the potential phase knowledge error sources, mass to power aperture product metrics, and increased complexity of the processing have lead to a new appreciation for the difficulties intrinsic to the sparse distributed array concept.

multi-satellite operations resulted in increased focus on aircraft flight test and ground modeling and simulation and a delay in the flight experiment. Operational issues that have yet to be addressed include high performance processors for on-orbit signal processing, operational target detection algorithms, data dissemination to operational systems, power aperture for operational area coverage and revisit rates, and broadband RF antenna technology.

Figure 16 – TechSat 21 Distributed Aperture Sensing Modes. [5]

6. CONCLUSION

Multi-mission RF sensing satellites potentially offer unique solutions for performing a broad range of mission applications in future systems. It is important to note that the 3-satellite TechSat 21 flight experiment was not designed to provide operational capability but rather to demonstrate technical feasibility of the concept. TechSat 21's RF sensing experiments were to record raw payload data to mass memory for downlink to the ground and subsequent data calibration and signal processing. Challenges in the areas of metrology, signal processing, and

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